

Stability Constants of *N*-Ethoxycarbonyl-*N*-[3-(*p*-anisyl)-pyrazol-5-yl]thiourea Complexes with some Transition Metal Ions. Synthesis and Characterisation of Copper(II) and Cobalt(II) Complexes

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Manuscript received 17 March 1989, revised 5 January 1993, accepted 19 January 1993

The formation constants of *N*-ethoxycarbonyl-*N*-[3-(*p*-anisyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-5-yl]thiourea (3) and *N*-ethoxycarbonyl-*N*-[3-(*p*-anisyl)pyrazol-5-yl]thiourea (4) with 3d-transition metals (Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II}) have been determined in 70% (v/v) ethanol-water medium. The formation constants both K_1 and K_2 follow the order: Mn^{II} < Ni^{II} < Co^{II} < Cu^{II} < Zn^{II}. Complexes of Cu^{II} and Co^{II} with ligand have been characterised by analytical, electrical conductivity, magnetic, ir and uv spectral data. The ligands form biscomplexes ML₂, where L is uninegatively charged and the binding sites are oxygen and sulphur atoms.

The chemistry of azolylthiourea has received considerable attention¹. Recently, our group have been involved in a programme for exploring the synthetic potential and utilities of azolylthiourea^{2,3}. As a part of this programme, the transition metal chemistry of azolylthiourea derivative has been investigated¹. We now report the solution stability of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of *N*-ethoxycarbonyl-*N*'-[3-(*p*-anisyl)pyrazol-5-yl]thiourea derivatives (3 and 4). The solid complexes of Cu^{II} and Co^{II} have been synthesised and characterised.

Results and Discussion

The formation constants of 3 and 4 with Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Mn^{II} were determined potentiometrically using the Bjerrum-Clavin⁵ titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossatti⁶. The protonation con-

stants were calculated from the formation curves (Figs. 1 and 2) for acid in presence and absence of ligand. The proton-ligand system was extended between 0 and 1 in the $\bar{n}_A$ scale and indicated that the ligands have one dissociable proton (Table 1).

TABLE I - FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SOME DIVALENT METAL ION CHELATES FORMED WITH COMPOUNDS 3 AND 4

Metal(II) ion	Formation constant for 3			Formation constant for 4		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log B ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log B ₂
H ⁺	9.620	—	9.620	10.43	—	10.43
	9.630	—	9.630	10.43	—	10.43
	9.625	—	9.625	10.43	—	10.43
Cu	7.930	6.960	14.89	7.67	7.00	14.67
	7.809	7.081	14.89	7.45	6.41	13.86
	7.830	7.060	14.89	7.51	7.16	14.67
	7.856	7.034	14.89	7.54	6.86	14.40
Ni	4.470	3.920	8.19	6.20	5.81	12.01
	4.204	4.186	8.39	5.93	6.12	13.05
	4.280	4.110	8.39	6.36	6.04	12.40
	4.318	4.072	8.39	6.16	5.99	12.15
Co	6.860	6.720	13.580			
	6.358	7.222	13.580			
	6.550	7.030	13.580			
	6.589	6.991	13.580			
Zn	5.290	4.825	10.115			
	4.983	5.132	10.115			
	5.080	5.035	10.115			
	5.118	4.997	10.115			
Mn	4.000	3.500	7.500	4.25	3.99	8.24
	3.710	3.789	7.499	3.83	4.40	8.25
	3.800	3.700	7.500	4.44	4.06	8.05
	3.837	3.663	7.500	4.17	4.15	8.32

Fig. 1 Formation curves for metal(II) chelates of 3 (●) Cu (■) Ni, (□) Co, (○) Zn and (△) Mn

The protonation constant $\log K_1$ was read directly from the graphs. $\log K_1^H$ was also calculated by the average value method. The protonation constant is assumed to be the $-\text{CSNHCO}-$ group. Each metal ion with the ligand was titrated with NaOH. Values of $\bar{n}$ obtained with all metal ions are above 1.5, indicating that in solution all the investigated metal ions react in two steps with the ligand, most likely forming firstly a 1 : 1 complex then a 1 : 2 complex. No indication of formation of other products was noticed. The formation constants of the complexes were found to follow the order: $\text{Mn}^{II} < \text{Ni}^{II} < \text{Co}^{II} < \text{Cu}^{II} > \text{Zn}^{II}$. Molar ratio⁷ and Job's continuous variation⁸ methods were used to confirm the stoichiometric ratio of the complexes.

The precipitated solid complexes of Cu^{II} and Co^{II} with compound 3 were isolated and their analytical, conductance and spectral data were determined (Table 2). The analytical data indicate that the isolated solid complexes are in ratio 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) in case of the Cu^{II} and 1 : 2 in case of the Co^{II} complexes. The molar conductance values of 10^{-3} molar solutions of the complexes in DMF show that the Cu^{II} complex is 1 : 2 electrolyte and the Co^{II} complex is non-electrolyte.

The ir spectra of the complexes reveal that the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ and ethoxycarbonyl groups are involved in the reaction. The $\text{C}=\text{S}$ band at 1535 cm^{-1} of the ligands did not appear in the spectra of the metal complexes. Moreover, the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ band appearing as strong band at 1715 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligands broadened and shifted to lower frequencies in the complex. Also, the bands of the complex revealed at 1650 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{O}$) and 1500 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{S}$), were not observed in the spectra of

the ligands. Based on these data structure 5 was suggested for the Cu^{II} -complex with 3.

Regarding the mode of chelation, magnetic susceptibility data taken along with ir spectra suggest the most probable configuration of the complexes. It has been found that the Cu^{II} complexes have low magnetic moments (0.16–0.22 B.M.) and such subnormal moments are suggestive of the presence of metal-metal interaction. Thus, structure 5 was suggested on the basis of the ir and magnetic susceptibility data.

This probable structure suggests that the metal reacts with the ligand through formation of ionic bond with liberation of a proton.

Further investigation on the structure of these complexes has been undertaken in order to provide more convincing evidence for the proposed structures.

Experimental

Solutions of the metal ions were prepared in double-distilled water from analytical grade $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and

 Formation curves for metal(II) chelates of **4**: (●) Cu, (■) Ni and (Δ) Mn.

MnCl₂·6H₂O. All the solutions were standardised by the reported established procedure⁹.

N-Ethoxycarbonyl-*N'*-[3-(*p*-anisyl)pyrazol-5-yl]-thioureas (**3** and **4**). *General procedure*: To a solution of ethoxycarbonylisothiocyanate³ (prepared from 0.12 mol of NH₄SCN and 0.1 mol of ethylchloroformate was refluxed in dry acetone for 5 min), 5-amino-3-(*p*-anisyl)-1-phenylpyrazole (**1**) or 5-amino-3-(*p*-anisyl)pyrazole (**2**) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h, then poured in cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol: **3** δ (DMSO-*d*₆), 1.6 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.0 (3H, s, CH₃O), 4.4 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.1 (1H, s, pyrazole CH-4); 7.2–8.0 (9H, m, ArH), 11.8 and

aqueous ethanol (1 : 1).

pH measurements were made at 25° using a Pye Cambridge pH-meter. The pH-meter readings were converted into [H⁺] using Uitert relation¹⁰. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Unicam Sp 1750 spectrophotometer, ir spectra on a Pye-Unicam Sp 1100 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a varian 60 A spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out using a Galileo-Sartorius air-damped analytical balance. Electric conductances of 10⁻³ molar solution of the complex in DMF at 25° were measured using a WTW LBRB conductivity bridge. Elemental

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Mol. formula	Colour	λ _m	M.p. ⁰ C	ν _{max} cm ⁻¹	Analysis %: Found / (Calcd.)				
						C	H	N	S	M
1	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	Pale yellow	—	146	1 535 (C=S), 1 715 (ester), 59.7	5.2	13.5	7.8		
					3 120–3 280 (NH)	(59.3	4.9	13.8	7.9)	
2	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	Pale yellow	—	150	1 540 (C=S), 1 740 (ester), 52.2	5.1	17.4	9.8		
					3 100–3 250 (NH)	(52.5	5.0	17.5	10.0)	
[Cu ₂ L ₂].2AcO	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ SCu	Dark green	126	—	1 650 Cu	52.1	3.9	11.9	6.9	13.9
						(52.3	4.1	12.2	7.0	13.8)
[CoL ₂]	Co(C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ S) ₂	Brown	13.8	—	1 655 Co	56.3	4.3	13.0	7.3	7.1

11.9 (2H, 2s, 2H); **4** δ 1.3 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.0 (3H, s, CH₃O), 4.2 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.2–7.8 (4H, m, Ar-H); 11.5 (H, s) and 13.2 (H, s).

Copper(II) and cobalt(II) chelates of the thiourea (**3**) were prepared in ratio 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal ion : ligand) respectively, by direct mixing of ethanolic solution of the metal salts to the ligand. The pH was raised to 7 and the solid complexes were washed with

analyses were obtained from Microanalytical Center at Cairo University.

Procedure: The following mixtures (A-C) were prepared for the determination of the acid dissociation constants of the ligand and formation constants of the metal complexes: (A) 3 ml of 0.1 M HCl + 5 ml of 1M NaCl, (B) mixture (A) + 10 ml of 0.01 M ligand solution and (C) mixture (B) + 4 ml of 0.005 M metal

ion solution. The final volume was made up to 40 ml in each case. The mixtures were made in 70% ethanolic aqueous solution and the ionic strength was 0.1 M. Each mixture was separately titrated with a carbonate-free 0.15 M NaOH in a N₂ atmosphere. From the pH-titration curves the values of $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated as previously reported¹¹.

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